

Prevalence and determinants of income among people with disabilities in Nepal: A cross-sectional study

Prasanna POUDEL^{1*}

¹Tribhuvan University, Kathmandu, Nepal. E-mail: wprasanna@gmail.com ORCID: 0009-0003-4325-0827

*Correspondence

Abstract

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Background: In Nepal, people with disabilities (PWDs) face significant economic challenges, with disparities in income and higher rates of poverty compared to the general population. This study aims to analyze the prevalence of poverty and determinants of income among PWDs, focusing on the impact of government allowances and other socio-economic factors.

Methods: Data were collected from 200 PWDs using a purposive sampling method. Information was gathered through face-to-face interviews and structured questionnaires. The analysis utilized the poverty line to assess poverty levels and multiple regression analysis to explore factors influencing income.

Results: The study found that 56.5% of PWDs live below the poverty line when government allowances are not considered, compared to 51% with allowances included. Government support was found to decrease the Gini coefficient by 0.10, indicating a reduction in income inequality. Key factors influencing income included education, work hours, experience, and access to assistive devices, while the severity of disability negatively affected income.

Conclusion: The findings highlight the critical role of government interventions in reducing poverty among PWDs. Enhanced support for health, education, and employment, as well as targeted policies to improve accessibility and integration, are essential for improving the economic well-being of PWDs in Nepal. The study underscores the need for policies that address the economic and social inclusion of PWDs to mitigate the high rates of poverty within this group.

Take-home message: Effective government support and proactive interventions are crucial to breaking the cycle of poverty for vulnerable groups. By strategically addressing the specific needs of these populations, such interventions not only alleviate immediate economic hardship but also foster long-term sustainable development and social inclusion.

Keywords: Income; people with disabilities; Nepal; poverty, poverty line, social security.

INTRODUCTION

Poverty is a complex phenomenon, ranging from being unable to meet the subsistence needs of food, shelter, and clothes to inadequate social, economic, and political participation. If poverty is measured based on whether subsistence essentials are met, it is absolute poverty. One way to measure absolute poverty is to use nationally or internationally defined poverty lines. People below the poverty line cannot meet subsistence necessities and fall into absolute poverty [1].

The Nepal Living Standards Survey (NLSS) 2022-23 has revised Nepal's poverty line and increased it from Nepalese rupees (NPR) 42,845 to NPR 72,908 per person per year. Nepalese citizens who earn less than NPR 72,908 per year fall into absolute poverty, and 20.27% of the population in Nepal lives below the new poverty line [2]. Based on the 2023 Mid-July exchange rate between Nepalese rupees and US dollar, that is, \$1 equivalent to NPR 131.17 [3], the revised poverty line is approximately equal to US dollar (\$) 556 per year per person.

One of the major determinants of the poverty level of individuals is their income level. People need sufficient money to meet their basic needs for food, clothes, shelter, health, and education. Higher-income groups enjoy better quality of life and social participation, while lower-income groups struggle to meet their subsistence needs. Other poverty factors include lack of capital, poor health, large families, lack of job opportunities or unemployment, and education [4]. People with disabilities (PWDs) are more likely to have less education, poorer health outcomes, lower levels of employment, and higher poverty rates [5]. Thus, PWDs are at substantial risk of poverty.

The latest population census -2021 of Nepal has shown that 2.2% of the total population in Nepal was disabled [6]. Based on the severity of disability, the government of Nepal has categorized PWDs into four categories: profound disability, severe disability, moderate disability, and mild disability, and they are issued red, blue, yellow, and white disability cards, respectively [7].

The government of Nepal has also been providing disability allowances for people with profound and severe disabilities to improve their well-being. People with profound disabilities and severe disabilities receive NPR 3,990 and NPR 2,128 per month, respectively [8].

Additionally, Nepal has adopted the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The “No Poverty” goal of SDGs includes eradicating extreme poverty from everywhere by 2030, which requires everyone to live on at least \$1.25 per day [9]. Vulnerable groups such as children, PWDs, minorities, and marginalized groups are less likely to be living on \$1.25 per day and are at substantial risk of extreme poverty.

Among the various vulnerable groups, PWDs have an added disadvantage because of their disability. In Nepal, the concept of disability is still rooted in superstition, i.e., disability is a result of past life sin [10] and negative karma either from past or present life [11]; as a result, PWDs are discriminated against in the society based on their disability, and they are excluded from social, economic, and political participation. Thus, PWDs are at higher risk of poverty in Nepal, and this study attempts to delve into poverty situations of PWDs, and factors that affect their income level in the Nepalese context. Thus, the study's research questions were as follows: (A) What is the prevalence of absolute poverty among PWDs in Nepal? (B) What are the key factors influencing the income level of PWDs?

METHODS

Data collection

The data for the study were collected from 200 PWDs using a purposive sampling method who fulfilled the following inclusion criteria:

- i. Must be at least 18 and younger than 60 years old.
- ii. Must be residents of Nepal.
- iii. Must hold disability cards issued by the government based on the medical diagnosis.

The required data and information were collected using face-to-face interviews. Data for this study were collected through structured questionnaires designed to capture detailed information relevant to the economic challenges faced by people with disabilities (PWDs) in Nepal. The questionnaire included sections on demographic information, income levels, employment status, disability type and severity, and access to government allowances and assistive devices. Prior to the actual data collection, the questionnaire was pilot-tested with a small subset of the target population to ensure the clarity and relevance of the questions. Adjustments were made based on feedback to ensure that the questions were culturally sensitive and accurately framed to elicit the necessary information.

The required data were collected in the year 2022. The collected data were organized in Excel, and the statistical software “R” was used for the analysis.

Data analysis

The national poverty line was used to identify the prevalence of poverty among PWDs, and the Gini coefficient was calculated to measure income inequalities. For any PWDs who fell below the national poverty line, NPR 72,908 per person per year were considered to indicate absolute poverty. The chi-square test was used to test the relationships between absolute poverty and factors such as gender, cause, type, and severity of disability. Multiple regression analysis was carried out to investigate the factors affecting the income of PWD.

Model specification

The dependent variable of the study is income earned by PWDs (including disability allowances), and the independent variables include age, years of schooling, gender, marital status, number of hours worked, experience, severity and types of disabilities, and access to assistive devices.

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 Age + \beta_2 Edu + \beta_3 Gen + \beta_4 Mri + \beta_5 Hrs + \beta_6 Exp + \beta_7 Sev + \beta_8 Typ + \beta_9 Ast + \mu \dots (1)$$

Table 1. Variable description of the model.

Variable Names	Description	Categories/Range	Reference Category
Dependent Variable			
Y	Yearly income of PWDs	Range: 0-1000000	-
Independent Variables			
Age	Age of PWDs	Range: 18-59	-
Edu	Years of schooling	Range: 0-18	-
Gen	Gender of PWDs	a. Female b. Male	Female
Mri	Marital status of PWDs	a. Married b. Single	Married
Hrs	Number of hours worked	Range: 0-11	-
Exp	Experience of PWDs at current work	Range: 0-15	-
Sev	Severity of disability	a. Mild b. Moderate c. Severe d. Profound	Mild
Typ	Type of disability	a. Physical impairment	Physical impairment

		b. Sensory impairment	
Ast	Access to assistive device	a. No	No
		b. Yes	

Ethical aspects

This study was conducted strictly to ethical standards to ensure all participants' dignity, rights, and welfare. All participants were informed about the study's aims, role, and right to withdraw without penalty. Written informed consent was obtained from each participant before proceeding with the interviews. Participants' confidentiality and anonymity were paramount. No personally identifiable information was collected in the questionnaires. All data were coded, and only aggregate data were reported in the findings. The study's ethical conduct followed the guidelines outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki, ensuring that all ethical concerns regarding research with human subjects were appropriately addressed.

RESULTS

Demographic features of PWD

The mean and median age of the overall PWDs in the study were 34.5 years and 32 years, respectively. The average family size of the PWD was small, and there was a greater prevalence of disability among males in the present study. The low mean (7.67) and median (5) years of schooling among PWDs indicate that many PWDs had not even completed school-level education.

When allowances provided by the government were not considered, the average annual income earned by PWDs was NPR 120,000, and the median income was NPR 50,000. Likewise, when allowances provided by the government were considered, the average income increased to NPR 139,000, and median income to NPR 60,000. The average income was much greater than the median income, indicating that few high-earning PWDs influenced the average. A low median income indicates that PWD's income is low- and that-income inequality may exist. The presence of income inequality was further indicated by a relatively high Gini coefficient value of 0.64 when allowance was not considered and 0.54 when allowance was considered. When allowances provided by the government were considered, the Gini coefficient decreased by 0.10. This indicates that government support is crucial to reduce income inequality among PWD. The other major demographic characteristics of the PWD included in the study are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Demographic features of PWD.

		Overall (N=200)
Age	Mean	34.5
	Median [Min, Max]	32.0 [18.0, 58.0]
Gender	Female	69 (34.5%)
	Male	131 (65.5%)
Family size	Mean	2.49
	Median [Min, Max]	3.00 [0, 6.00]
Years of schooling	Mean	7.67
	Median [Min, Max]	5.00 [0, 18.0]
Marital Status	Married	71 (35.5%)

		Overall (N=200)
	Single	129 (64.5%)
Total income without allowances	Mean	120,000
	Median [Min, Max]	50,000 [0, 1,000,000]
	Gini coefficient	0.64
Total income with allowances	Mean	139,000
	Median [Min, Max]	60,000 [0, 1,000,000]
	Gini coefficient	0.54
Hours worked	Mean	4.13
	Median [Min, Max]	5.00 [0, 11.0]
Experience	Mean	3.46
	Median [Min, Max]	0.5 [0, 15]
Assistive device	No	63 (31.5%)

Prevalence of Poverty among PWDs using national poverty line 2022/2023

The national poverty line of Nepal, NPR 72,908 was used in the study to determine absolute poverty. Absolute poverty was determined by considering the annual income of PWDs with and without allowances, and the results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Poverty analysis based on the poverty line 2022/2023.

	Mild (N=35)	Moderate (N=51)	Severe (N=66)	Profound (N=48)	Overall (N=200)
With allowance					
Above poverty line	29 (82.9%)	23 (45.1%)	37 (56.1%)	9 (18.8%)	98 (49.0%)
Below poverty line	6 (17.1%)	28 (54.9%)	29 (43.9%)	39 (81.3%)	102 (51.0%)
<i>Note:</i> Chi-square test	$\chi^2 = 35.2583$ df = 3 p-value = .00				
Without allowance					
Above poverty line	29 (82.9%)	23 (45.1%)	28 (42.4%)	7 (14.6%)	87 (43.5%)
Below poverty line	6 (17.1%)	28 (54.9%)	38 (57.6%)	41 (85.4%)	113 (56.5%)

Note: Chi-square test: $\chi^2 = 38.4732$ df = 3 p = .000

Table 3 shows that without the allowances provided by the government, there is a high absolute poverty rate among people with profound disabilities, followed by severe disabilities, moderate disabilities, and mild disabilities. As the government does not provide allowances to people with mild and moderate disabilities, their absolute poverty rate remained unchanged when disability allowances were considered. However, allowances provided to people with profound and severe disability have helped

to reduce the poverty rate in this group and have reduced the overall absolute poverty rate among PWDs by 5.5 percentage points. The chi-square test calculated to investigate the relationship between the severity of disability and poverty (with and without allowance) had a p-value less than 0.05, indicating a significant relationship between poverty and the severity of disability.

The gender-based absolute poverty rate

In the study, there was a greater prevalence of poverty among females with disabilities than among males with disabilities. A chi-square test was calculated to investigate the relationship between poverty and gender.

Table 4. Relationships between poverty and gender.

Absolute poverty, considering allowance			
Gender	Above poverty line	Below poverty line	Total
Female	24(34.8%)	45(65.2%)	69
Male	74(56.5%)	57(43.5%)	131
Total	98 (49%)	102(51%)	200

Note: Chi-square test: $\chi^2 = 7.6744$ df = 1 p = .0056

The p-value of the chi-square test is less than 0.05, indicating that there is a significant relationship between gender and poverty (χ^2 (1, N = 200) = 7.6744, p = .0056).

Absolute poverty based on disability type

In this study, 53.5% of the respondents had a physical impairment, and 46.5% had a sensory impairment. Table 5 shows that people with a physical impairment had a greater prevalence of poverty than people with sensory impairment. The chi-square test was used to investigate the relationship between poverty and disability types.

Table 5. Relationships between poverty and disability type.

Absolute poverty, considering Allowance	Physical impairment	Sensory impairment	Total
Above poverty line	45(45.9%)	53(54.1%)	98(100.0%)
Below poverty line	62(60.8%)	40(39.2%)	102(100.0%)
Total	107(53.5%)	93(46.5%)	200(100.0%)

Note: Chi-square test: $\chi^2 = 3.8625$ df = 1 p = .0494

The p-value of the chi-square test is less than 0.05, indicating that there is a significant relationship between disability type and poverty (χ^2 (1, N = 200) = 3.8625, p = .0494).

Absolute poverty rate based on the cause of disability

The majority of PWD in the study were born with disabilities, followed by being disabled by accidents and diseases. PWDs who were disabled since birth were at greater risk of being poor, as shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Relationships between poverty and causes of disability.

Absolute poverty, considering Allowance	Accident	Birth	Disease	Total
Above poverty line	36 (53.7%)	35(39.8%)	27(60.0%)	98(49.0%)
Below poverty line	31(46.3%)	53(60.2%)	18(40.0%)	102(51.0%)

Total	67(100.0%)	88 (100.0%)	45 (100.0%)	200(100.0%)
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Note: Chi-square test : $\chi^2 = 5.7773$ df = 2 p = .0557

The chi-square test was used to investigate the relationship between poverty and the cause of disability. As the p-value of the chi-square test was greater than 0.05, there was no statistically significant relationship between poverty and the cause of disability (χ^2 (2, N = 200) = 5.7773, p = .0557).

Factors influencing the income of PWD

The dependent variable of the study is the income of the PWD, and the independent variables are age, education, gender, marital status, hours worked, experience, severity and types of disability, and access to assistive devices. Multiple regression analysis was carried out to investigate the factors that influence the income of PWD, and the results of the multiple regression analysis are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Result of multiple regression analysis.

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	P value
Intercept	-42,899.12	45,361.53	-0.95	0.35
Age	175.21	875.68	0.20	0.84
Years of schooling	2,905.44	1,406.54	2.07	0.04*
Gender: Male	30,881.21	15,553.33	1.99	0.048*
Marital status: Single	8,972.78	17,863.22	0.50	0.62
Hours worked	19,242.45	2,411.81	7.98	0.00*
Experience	7,777.99	2,058.90	3.78	0.00*
Severity: Moderate	-55,717.73	25,209.72	-2.21	0.03*
Severity: Profound	-5,978.66	29,643.39	-0.20	0.84
Severity: Severe	-19,821.61	26,804.13	-0.74	0.46
Types: Sensory	36,541.01	16,735.62	2.18	0.03*
Assistive devices: Yes	39,287.16	19,668.90	2.00	0.047*
R-squared		0.5814		
Adjusted R-squared		0.557		
F-statistics		23.74		0.00

Dependent variable: Yearly income with allowances

Note: * P < 0.05

Table 7 shows that factors such as education, gender, severity and types of disabilities, assistive devices, hours worked, and experience are significantly related to the income of PWD. While keeping other factors constant, a one-year increase in years of schooling increases the income of PWDs by NPR 2,905.44 per year. Similarly, males with disabilities earned NPR 30,881.21 per year more than females with disabilities while keeping other factors constant. When the working hours of PWDs increase by one hour per day, their annual income increases by NPR 19,242.45, holding other things constant. Similarly, each year, the increase in the experience of PWDs increases their yearly income by NPR 7,777.99.

People with sensory impairment earned NPR 36,541.01 per year, more than people with physical impairment. Other things being constant, people with moderate disability earn NPR 55,717.73 per year, less than people with mild disabilities. Likewise,

PWD who have access to assistive devices earn annually, NPR 39,287.16 more than PWD who do not have access to assistive devices.

The adjusted R-squared of the model is 0.557, indicating that the model explained 55.7% of the variation in the income of PWD. The p-value of the F-statistic of the model was less than 0.05, indicating that the model was statistically significant.

The autocorrelation in the model was checked using the Durbin–Watson test, heteroskedasticity in the model was checked using the Breusch–Pagan test, and the multicollinearity of independent variables in the model was checked by the generalized variance inflation factor.

Table 8. Assumption of regression analysis.

Generalized variance inflation factor			
Independent variable	GVIF	Df	GVIF^{1/(2*Df)}
Age	1.79	1.00	1.34
Years of schooling	1.40	1.00	1.18
Gender	1.11	1.00	1.05
Severity	2.36	3.00	1.15
Type	1.41	1.00	1.19
Marital status	1.48	1.00	1.22
Assistive device	1.69	1.00	1.30
Working hours	1.91	1.00	1.38
Experience	2.22	1.00	1.49
Durbin Watson test			
Dwtest	1.96		0.3399
Breusch-Pagan test			
Bptest	19.101	11	0.06

The generalized variance inflation factor was used to diagnose multicollinearity in the model. The common rule is that multicollinearity exists if the value of GVIF is between 5 and 10. However, the GVIF values of the independent variables are less than 5. Thus, the model fulfilled the assumption that independent variables are not highly correlated.

The Durbin-Watson test value of 1.96 is close to 2, confirming no autocorrelation in the model. Additionally, in the Breusch–Pagan test, the p-value is greater than 0.05, confirming the model fulfilled the assumption of homoscedasticity of the error term.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The study revealed that the absolute poverty rates among PWDs with and without considering allowances were 51% and 56.5%, respectively, which was higher than the absolute poverty rate (20.27%) of Nepal [2], indicating that PWDs were less likely to meet their subsistence needs and are at greater risk of being in poverty than the general population. PWDs are not only at risk of income poverty and food insecurity but also vulnerable to violence and exclusion from health, education, work, and social security [12]. However, other research conducted by Banks et al. [13] in the districts of Cam Le, Vietnam, and Tanahun, Nepal, concluded that there was no significant difference in the incidence of monetary poverty between people with and without disabilities. The present study's findings might contradict the previous research conducted by Bank et al. because the earlier studies were based on the old poverty line of Nepal, which is lower than the revised poverty line 2022/2023. Likewise, the Gini

coefficient of Nepal based on the wealth in the fiscal year 2022/2023 is 0.24 [14], while the calculated Gini coefficient of PWDs in the study was much higher at 0.54 while considering the allowance and 0.64 when allowances were not considered. This indicates that people with disabilities are experiencing higher income inequality compared to the general population.

It should be noted that the disability allowances have helped to reduce poverty among PWDs by 5.5 percentage points and the Gini coefficient by 0.10. This indicates that social security provided by the government is essential to reduce poverty and income inequalities among PWD. Thus, the government should revise the existing disability allowances and implement targeted policies that encourage the social and economic integration of PWDs.

There was a greater prevalence of poverty among females, people with physical impairment, and people with more severe disabilities. The chi-squared test confirmed that the severity, type, and gender of the PWD were significantly associated with the poverty rate of the PWD. Even in developed countries such as Canada, women with disabilities and PWDs living alone have the highest poverty rate, and people with the most severe disabilities are the poorest [15].

One critical factor determining absolute poverty among PWDs is their income from diverse sources, such as income from their own business or work and allowances received from the government. Multiple regression analysis indicated that education, working hours, experience, and access to assistive devices positively affected the income of PWDs. In contrast, the severity of a disability had a negative effect on the income of PWDs. Additionally, it was found that male with disabilities were earning more than female with disabilities. Thus, it is recommended that local governments focus on ensuring health, education, and employment as well as promoting training for PWDs to alleviate the poverty of this vulnerable group of people.

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